

METHODOLOGY OF WORKING ON MEANINGFUL GROUPS OF ADJECTIVES IN PRIMARY CLASSES

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Abstract: this article describes the methods and tools used in this process for elementary school students to work on the semantic groups of adjectives. This article is relevant as it provides theoretical information supported by scientific views, as well as guidelines for the practical application of certain methods and tools. Methods and tools were developed within four stages of primary classes.

Key words: adjective, semantic group, tool, process, method, practical knowledge, concept, program.

In linguistics, the system of studying the adjective word group, slightly different from other word groups, implies the following:

Lexical enrichment of the material;

Grammatical enrichment of the material;

And the last one implies a gradual complicating of the above.

In the first grade, students learn the lexical meaning of the adjective, that is, how? To have answers to their questions;

In the second class, spiritual groups (internal division, size, shape, color, taste, etc.);

In the third and fourth stages, some spelling features of words related to quality levels and quality vocabulary are taught.

In our linguistics, the process of learning each word group is based on its own characteristics, and the quality word group is based on linguistic features.

Adjectives refer to animate and inanimate objects in existence, and are divided into the following groups based on this:

Qualities of color;

Taste qualities;

Shape qualities;
Adjectives of size;
Qualities of character;
Space-time qualities;
Odor qualities;
Weight qualities are such as.

One of the most effective ways to teach adjectives to elementary school students is to teach them by linking them to nouns. Because the noun group represents a person and thing as an independent word group in linguistics. Adjectives, as mentioned above, indicate their sign. We are the first to introduce this method to readers through our scientific work on this topic we thought it would be better to explain consciously from the class. If all attention is focused on this, students will begin to consciously understand information about adjectives, even at a young age. The relationship between a noun and an adjective word group is gradually becoming more complicated and defined. In short, the study of the semantic and some grammatical features of the adjective word group is carried out morphologically and partially syntactically.

The traditional language learning process is often focused on repetition and rote learning. But younger students want to learn through experience and engagement. Here are some suggestions on how to make learning fun with these fun and easy adjective word games. In the case of integration with students' daily life, the following questions can be used to find out how to make it interesting to learn about quality vocabulary in their minds with language games related to the Bible. It is possible to form knowledge, skills and competences about adjective vocabulary in the students' minds by means of the following questions in the case of integration with the daily life styles of the students. For example, speak briefly about yourself, list your qualities. This process is different qualities are formed. In this process, the student will learn about adjectives and learn about the characteristics of your friends in the class. The second way is the interactive method under the name of quality matching. A set of cards is created with different

adjectives written on each card. Also, the teacher needs some pictures that can be described with adjectives (for example, magazine pictures, travel brochures, etc.). Now let's get acquainted with how the game works:

Each player chooses a picture. Each player is dealt four cards. If the player can describe the image with all four cards, he wins. If not, he discards the card and draws a new card from the pile. The game continues until the winner is determined.

Another interactive method created with the help of new technologies is the "show the name" game. In this process, students are divided into two or more teams. Then the name or it is displayed on the board as a picture. Teams are given one minute to write as many adjectives as possible. Teams receive points for each quality they match. Research shows that this game increases students' imagination and thinking, including vocabulary.

Show and tell game.

In the process of organizing this game, students brought different things from home. And they describe them in front of the class. The teacher records all the adjectives that the student uses to describe the object.

"Describe the day."

Describing a Day Like Show and Tell Students come to the front of the class and use adjectives to describe their day.

"riddle using adjectives" game.

These qualities make it an interesting game that tests the student's creativity and understanding. Elementary students drawing animals, people, vehicles and other horses using adjectives for "Who am I?" they come up with riddles. Then the riddles are read out to the whole class and analyzed. Unlike the above games, this game requires students to take into account young characteristics. That is, conducting it in the fourth and third grades will have a positive effect.

According to a number of experienced scientists and psychologists of foreign countries, young children tend to create interesting stories. Applying this through the following game is highly effective.

“Journey to Favorite Stories with Adjectives.” In this game, first, students make up a short story based on their abilities based on connected speech. And these stories are read out and their qualities are analyzed.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it can be said that there are various methods and tools in the process of teaching the semantic groups of adjectives. The teacher uses them according to his skills. The creation of methods depends on the creative thinking and ideas of the pedagogue. It should be noted that the methods and tools should be suitable for the opportunities and age characteristics of the students.

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